

ISic3712

I.Sicily inscription 3712

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication (?)

Material

marble

Object

basin

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

found in excavations of the ekklesiastikon at S. Nicola

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale
Archeologico Pietro Griffo, inventory 7629

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR136024

1. [--- Ἀπ]ελλᾶ ἱερ [ατεύσσα---]

Edition: PHI336048

1. [— — — Ἀπ]ελλᾶ ἱερ [ατεύουσα — — —]

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 136024

PHI 336048

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1266.4

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 36 no.4 fig.81

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